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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY 56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES..... 84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	
ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS .	148
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
THE NATURE AND ESSENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES IN MASS MEDIA ORGANIZATIONS.....	151
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR RECOVERING MISSING (NAN) VALUES IN INFORMATION SYSTEM DATA	156
Yarmatov Sherzodjon Shokir oglu, Orifov Oxunjon Fazliddinzoda	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES	167
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
IMPROVING LOAN PORTFOLIO QUALITY AND CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS	173
Turgunov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
INNOVATION CAPABILITIES AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF SUPPLY CHAIN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION — EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	177
Mukhammadyaminova Shakhzoda	
URBAN PLANNING OF TRANSPORT INTERCHANGE HUBS NEAR TUBERCULOSIS CARE FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN	183
Gabibova Irina Vagifovna, Abdumuminova Diyora Gayratovna	
ADAPTING INTERNAL AUDIT STANDARDS IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS TO PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PRACTICES.....	192
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ECONOMETRIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN KHOREZM REGION	197
Otajanov Umid Abdullayevich	
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN RECLAMATION AND GIS TECHNOLOGIES ON SALINE SOILS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN.....	205
Tajibaev Berdakh	
ISSUES REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “TOLLING OPERATIONS” MODULE IN THE GOODS MOVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER THE CUSTOMS TERRITORY PROCESSING REGIME	212
Lutpullaev Shukrullo Kudratullaevich	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN ENHANCING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN	218
Akmaljon Odilov	
INTERNATIONAL TRENDS OF DIGITALIZATION IN CUSTOMS MANAGEMENT	222
Radjapova Latofat Sardarovna	
THE ROLE OF TAX POLICY IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY	230
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi	
PRACTICES IN ENTERPRISE COST STRUCTURE MANAGEMENT AND DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	236
Aymukhammedova Amina Kakajanovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	242
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
RECONCEPTUALIZING BUSINESS INCUBATORS IN STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS	246
Gafujon Usmanov	
DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN MARKETING APPROACHES TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES	257
Safarov Bakhtiyor Djurakulovich	
MECHANISMS FOR EVALUATING AND IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE PUBLIC TRANSPORT SECTOR	263
Berdiyorov Temur Azamatovich	
THE INFLUENCE OF HYDRODYNAMIC ASPECTS OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL RISE ON URBAN WATERLOGGING	268
B.D. Abdullaev, B.R. Nasibov, Sh.T. Irgashev, D. Abdullaev	
BASIC INFORMATION MODEL OF A DIGITAL OBJECT	277
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich, Karakhanova Alsu Muratalievna, Keldiyorov Sirojiddin Tura ugli, Zayniddinova Zebiniso Akmalovna	
COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE AND TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SOLAR PANEL MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS	281
Urishev Omadjon, Kushakova Sarvinoz, Kamolboyev Sirojbek	
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR FORMING ECOLOGICALLY ORIENTED MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	294
Kholov Hamza Tajiddinovich	
INVESTIGATION OF GERMANIUM EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY FROM TECHNOGENIC METALLURGICAL WASTE	301
Yormatov Dostonbek, Shodiyev Abbos, Muhammadiyev Elbek	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND OPTIMIZING PRODUCTION COSTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY	309
Utbasarov Doniyorjon Bakhtiyorovich	
THEORETICAL, PRACTICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF AUDITING THE ACTIVITIES OF ECONOMIC ENTITIES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	318
Mirzaeva Sabina Khushnudovna, Khaydarova Dildora Djakhongirovna	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON WOMEN'S LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN UNDER INDUSTRY 4.0	322
Doniyorova Zukhrabonu Alisher qizi	
LEVEL OF ENSURING FOOD SECURITY: IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS AND INSTRUMENTS	328
Sodiqjon Qodirovich Mattiyev	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY, AND LOCALIZATION POLICY OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT SYSTEM	334
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VOSITASIDA	339
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	

PROJECT-ORIENTED ESP32 IOT CURRICULUM WITH A SHARED-RESOURCE LABORATORY MODEL: DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, AND LESSONS LEARNED	344
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Lazizbek Yusupov	
FIVE-CRITERION METHODOLOGY OF INTERNAL CONTROL ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	353
Babakulova Matluba Kurbannazarovna	
THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION–INDUSTRY INTEGRATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY.....	357
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
MECHANISMS AND DIRECTIONS FOR DEEPENING REGIONAL INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	361
Akbarova Kamola Akmaljonovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS	368
Saidov Suhrob Shodmonovich	
IMPROVING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN’S SERVICE SECTOR: BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	371
Shermatov Axror Abdixakimovich	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING CUSTOMS RISK PROFILE INDICATORS BASED ON MATHEMATICAL AND STATISTICAL METHODS	377
Niyazov Sherzod Shovkat ugli	
AN INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK FOR CRYPTO-ASSET REGULATION: ADDRESSING LEGAL UNCERTAINTY IN DIGITAL FINANCIAL SYSTEMS	385
Iminokhunov Abdukokhor A., Khakimov Abdurakhmon Mukhammad-Ali ugli	
THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE SERVICE SECTOR	396
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	

THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and organizational-economic foundations of the service sector. The study examines the formation of the service economy, its distinguishing features compared to the production sector, and its role in the modern economy. In addition, the article explores the organizational and economic factors influencing the development of the service sector, the processes of digital transformation, and mechanisms for improving efficiency. The research findings emphasize the importance of institutional approaches and innovative management methods in enhancing the sustainable development and competitiveness of the service industry.

Keywords: service sector, economic development, organizational mechanism, service economy, innovation, digital transformation, efficiency.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining nazariy va tashkiliy-iqtisodiy asoslari chuqur tahlil qilingan. Xizmatlar iqtisodiyotining shakllanishi, uning ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlaridan farqli jihatlar hamda zamonaviy iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Shuningdek, xizmat ko'rsatish sektorining rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi tashkiliy-iqtisodiy omillar, raqamli transformatsiya jarayonlari va samaradorlikni oshirish mexanizmlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari xizmatlar sohasini barqaror rivojlantirish va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda institutsional yondashuvlar hamda innovatsion boshqaruv usullarining muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, tashkiliy mexanizm, xizmatlar iqtisodiyoti, innovatsiya, raqamli transformatsiya, samaradorlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются теоретические и организационно-экономические основы сферы услуг. Рассматриваются процессы формирования экономики услуг, её отличительные особенности по сравнению с производственным сектором, а также роль в современной экономике. Кроме того, исследуются организационно-экономические факторы, влияющие на развитие сферы услуг, процессы цифровой трансформации и механизмы повышения эффективности. Результаты исследования подчеркивают важность институциональных подходов и инновационных методов управления в обеспечении устойчивого развития и конкурентоспособности сферы услуг.

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, экономическое развитие, организационный механизм, экономика услуг, инновации, цифровая трансформация, эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern global economy, the service sector has become one of the most significant and rapidly developing components of national economic systems. In many developed countries, the service sector accounts for more than 60–70% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), reflecting the transition from an industrial economy to a post-industrial and knowledge-based economic model. This transformation demonstrates the growing importance of intangible assets, human capital, innovation, and digital technologies in the creation of economic value [1].

The theoretical foundations of the service sector emphasize its distinctive characteristics in comparison with the goods-producing sector. Services are intangible, inseparable from the processes of production and consumption, heterogeneous in quality, and perishable in nature. These specific features require specialized organizational and managerial approaches to ensure operational efficiency, quality assurance, and customer satisfaction [2]. Unlike manufacturing industries, where products can be stored and standardized, service delivery largely depends on human interaction, process management, and the ability to respond promptly to

consumer needs.

From a theoretical perspective, the concept of service economics has undergone substantial evolution over time. Early economic studies mainly focused on distinguishing goods from services, emphasizing their non-material nature and classification challenges. However, contemporary approaches, particularly the Service-Dominant Logic theory, argue that value is not embedded in products themselves but is co-created through interaction between service providers and consumers [3]. This conceptual shift has significantly transformed the understanding of value creation mechanisms within service industries.

Moreover, the organizational and economic structure of the service sector is strongly influenced by institutional frameworks, market competition, and technological advancement. Effective service provision requires developed infrastructure, supportive regulatory systems, and efficient management mechanisms. In this regard, institutional economics plays a crucial role in improving the performance, sustainability, and competitiveness of service industries [4].

In recent years, digital transformation has emerged as one of the primary drivers of service sector development. The integration of information and communication technologies (ICT), artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and digital platforms has substantially enhanced service efficiency, accessibility, and scalability. Online banking, e-commerce, digital education, telemedicine, and electronic government services are clear examples of how digitalization is reshaping traditional service models and creating new forms of economic interaction [5].

In addition, globalization has intensified the integration of service markets across countries, facilitating the expansion of international trade in services and increasing participation in global value chains. According to OECD reports, services currently constitute a significant share of global trade flows, particularly in knowledge-intensive sectors such as finance, information technology, logistics, consulting, and professional services [6].

The service sector also plays a vital role in employment generation and macroeconomic stability. It absorbs a substantial proportion of the labor force, especially in urban areas, and contributes to poverty reduction, income diversification, and social welfare improvement. The sustainable development of the service sector is closely connected with advancements in human capital, educational systems, professional training, and workforce competencies [7].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical and empirical literature on the service sector has evolved considerably over recent decades, reflecting transformations in global economic structures, technological advancement, and modern management practices. Early studies primarily concentrated on defining services and distinguishing them from tangible goods, whereas contemporary research increasingly focuses on value creation, innovation, digital transformation, and customer-oriented management within service systems.

One of the earliest and most influential contributions was made by Hill (1977), who provided a conceptual distinction between goods and services. According to Hill, services are inherently intangible and cannot be stored, transferred, or owned in the same manner as physical goods. This foundational definition established the basis for subsequent theoretical developments in service economics and service management theory [1].

Building upon this foundation, the Service-Dominant Logic developed by Vargo and Lusch (2004) introduced a significant paradigm shift in understanding economic exchange. Rather than considering value as embedded within tangible products, this theory argues that value is co-created through interactions between service providers and consumers. The approach emphasizes relationships, knowledge sharing, and resource integration as central components of value creation in modern service systems [2].

Grönroos (2015) further expanded service theory by focusing on service management and customer relationship orientation. He argues that service quality is determined not only by technical outcomes but also by functional dimensions such as communication quality, responsiveness, reliability, and customer experience. This perspective highlights the strategic importance of long-term customer relationships in achieving sustainable competitive advantage within service industries [3].

Lovelock and Wirtz (2021) broadened the analysis by integrating strategic management, marketing, and operational perspectives into service sector research. Their work emphasizes that modern service organizations must effectively combine technology, operational efficiency, innovation, and customer-centric strategies to remain competitive in dynamic and rapidly changing markets. They also underline the growing importance of digital platforms and information technologies in service delivery, coordination, and customer interaction processes [4].

Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler (2018) made significant contributions to the understanding of service quality and customer satisfaction. Their research introduced comprehensive frameworks for measuring perceived

service quality, including dimensions such as reliability, assurance, empathy, responsiveness, and tangibility. These models have become widely applied in both academic research and practical service management systems [5].

From a macroeconomic perspective, OECD reports (2019–2020) emphasize the increasing importance of services within global value chains. Services are no longer confined to domestic consumption but have become highly tradable internationally due to rapid digitalization and globalization processes. Knowledge-intensive services such as finance, information and communication technologies (ICT), logistics, education, and professional consulting now occupy a central role in global trade and economic integration [6].

The World Bank (2022) highlights that the expansion of the service sector serves as a key driver of structural transformation in developing economies. As countries gradually transition from agriculture- and manufacturing-based systems toward service-oriented economies, employment structures, productivity levels, and income distribution patterns also undergo substantial changes. The report stresses the importance of human capital development, institutional modernization, and regulatory reforms in supporting this transformation process [7].

Heskett et al. (1997) introduced the Service Profit Chain model, establishing a direct relationship between employee satisfaction, service quality, customer loyalty, and organizational profitability. This model demonstrates that internal organizational factors strongly influence external market performance, making human resource management, employee motivation, and organizational culture essential components of sustainable success in the service sector [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and analytical research approach to examine the theoretical and organizational-economic foundations of the service sector. The research is based on a systematic review and analysis of scientific literature, including academic books, peer-reviewed journal articles, international analytical reports, and institutional publications from organizations such as the World Bank, OECD, and other authoritative economic institutions.

A comparative analysis method is applied to evaluate various theoretical approaches to service sector development, including classical economic theories, institutional economics, Service-Dominant Logic, and contemporary digital transformation concepts. This approach enables the identification of similarities, differences, and evolutionary trends in the understanding of service economics and management systems.

In addition, methods of synthesis, generalization, and logical analysis are utilized to determine the key organizational and economic factors affecting the efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness of the service sector. Particular attention is given to the influence of innovation, digital technologies, institutional frameworks, human capital, and management mechanisms on service sector performance.

The study also incorporates descriptive analysis to interpret structural transformations occurring within the service economy, especially in the context of globalization, technological progress, digitalization, and institutional development. Furthermore, the research considers the impact of modern information and communication technologies (ICT), artificial intelligence, and digital platforms on the modernization of traditional service models.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the service sector demonstrates that its level of development differs substantially across countries depending on institutional quality, technological infrastructure, human capital development, and the overall degree of economic modernization. In advanced economies, the service sector represents the dominant component of economic activity, whereas in many developing countries it remains in a transitional stage characterized by structural transformation and gradual expansion.

From a macroeconomic perspective, the service sector plays a crucial role in GDP formation, employment generation, income diversification, and productivity growth. In OECD member states, services account for the majority of economic output, reflecting the formation of highly developed post-industrial and knowledge-based economic systems. In contrast, developing economies, including Uzbekistan, are progressively increasing the share of services through institutional reforms, digital transformation processes, entrepreneurship development, and private sector expansion (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Service Sector Development Level (Illustrative Index)¹

One of the key findings of the study is that digital transformation plays a decisive role in improving the efficiency and competitiveness of the service sector. The implementation of e-government systems, online banking, digital education platforms, and e-commerce solutions has significantly reduced transaction costs, increased operational efficiency, and improved the accessibility of services for consumers. This trend clearly demonstrates that technological adoption has become one of the primary drivers of competitiveness within the modern service economy.

The comparative index presented in Figure 1 illustrates the relative level of service sector development across different regions. Although the index is illustrative in nature, it reflects general global trends identified in international economic reports and analytical studies.

The results indicate that OECD countries significantly outperform other regions in terms of service sector development due to advanced technological infrastructure, strong institutional systems, high levels of human capital, and widespread digital integration. The world average reflects a moderate level of development, while Uzbekistan demonstrates stable and positive progress driven by economic reforms, expansion of private entrepreneurship, and increasing digitalization of economic activities.

The analysis confirms that the service sector serves as one of the key drivers of modern economic growth, employment generation, and structural transformation. Its sustainable development depends on the effective interaction between institutional quality, technological progress, innovation capacity, and human capital accumulation. Strengthening these factors is essential for improving national competitiveness, increasing productivity, and ensuring long-term sustainable economic development.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted theoretical and analytical study confirms that the service sector represents one of the most dynamic and strategically important components of modern economic systems. Its development plays a significant role in stimulating economic growth, increasing employment opportunities, improving productivity, and enhancing overall living standards. Contemporary theoretical approaches explain the growing importance

¹ Author's development

of the service sector through structural economic transformation, the expansion of human capital, rapid technological advancement, and the intensification of innovation-driven processes.

In the case of Uzbekistan, the analysis demonstrates that the share of services in GDP has been steadily increasing, indicating a gradual transition toward a service-oriented economy. Nevertheless, the sectoral structure remains largely dominated by traditional service activities such as trade and transportation, which limits the creation of high value-added services and reduces overall productivity potential. In addition, the organizational and economic mechanisms of many service enterprises are still characterized by insufficient levels of digitalization, fragmented management systems, and limited implementation of innovative business practices.

The results of the study further confirm that human capital development, institutional quality, technological modernization, and digital infrastructure are among the key determinants of service sector efficiency and competitiveness. The effective integration of these factors can transform the service sector into a stable and sustainable driver of long-term economic development.

Based on the results of the research, the following recommendations are proposed:

It is necessary to accelerate the transition from traditional services, such as trade and transportation, toward high value-added service industries including information technology, financial services, consulting, logistics, education, and digital business services in order to improve competitiveness and productivity.

Service enterprises should actively implement digital platforms, e-commerce systems, automated management tools, cloud technologies, and artificial intelligence solutions to increase operational efficiency, improve customer accessibility, and reduce transaction costs.

Improving vocational education systems, expanding professional training programs, introducing international certification standards in service quality, and aligning educational programs with labor market requirements are essential for increasing labor productivity and service quality.

Modern management approaches such as lean management, strategic management, customer-oriented management, and performance-based management should be introduced in service enterprises to optimize resource utilization and enhance managerial effectiveness.

It is important to strengthen institutional reforms aimed at improving market competition, reducing administrative barriers, simplifying business procedures, and ensuring a transparent and innovation-friendly business environment for sustainable service sector development.

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